

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Employee Voice and Worker Well-being in the Nigerian oil and Gas sector: Empirical Evidence from Selected Companies in Rivers State

Cletus Okey Amah* and Destiny Chigozie Ikeagwu

Department of Management, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Port Harcourt Business School, Nigeria.

International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 15(03), 949-966

Publication history: Received on 04 May 2025; revised on 11 June 2025; accepted on 13 June 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.15.3.1825>

Abstract

It is commonly argued that organizations that suppress employee voice will generally witness increased job dissatisfaction, burnout, and workplace conflicts, which ultimately affect employee retention and overall well-being. Empirical evidence abounds to the effect that when employees feel heard and valued in decision-making processes, they are more likely to experience reduced stress, increased motivation, and better workplace relationships, ultimately contributing to higher productivity and organizational performance. However, despite the growing body of literature on the putative link between the workplace wellbeing of workers and the latitude of expression accorded them therein, research in this regard within Nigeria's oil and gas sector remains limited.

This study set out to empirically investigate the relationship between employee voice (our predictor variable) and worker well-being (our criterion variable) in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. Adopting a cross-sectional survey research design, relevant data were collected from 245 employees using structured questionnaire. The study variables were assessed for validity and reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients ranging from 0.779 to 0.876. The results, analyzed using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation and hypotheses testing via SPSS 26, revealed that Direct Voice had the strongest positive correlation with worker well-being ($r = 0.718$ to 0.750), emphasizing the importance of open communication channels. Indirect Voice also showed a significant but slightly weaker correlation ($r = 0.617$ to 0.647), suggesting that while representation through unions is beneficial, it is perceived as less immediate. Leadership style demonstrated a strong influence on psychological well-being ($r = 0.775$), reinforcing the role of transformational leadership in fostering a supportive work environment. The study recommends that organizations implement policies promoting direct employee participation, strengthen the effectiveness of indirect representation, and enhance leadership development programmes to improve overall worker well-being.

Keywords: Employee Voice; Direct Voice; Indirect Voice; Leadership Style; Worker Well-Being; Psychological Well-Being; Social Well-Being; Physical Well-Being

1. Introduction

The oil and gas sector in Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, plays a crucial role in the country's economic development. However, the industry is also characterized by high job demands, safety risks, and industrial relations challenges that significantly impact worker well-being. Employee voice, which refers to the ability of workers to express their opinions, concerns, and suggestions regarding workplace policies and conditions, has been identified as a critical factor in enhancing job satisfaction, psychological well-being, and overall work engagement (Dundon et al., 2004). When employees feel heard and valued in decision-making processes, they are more likely to experience reduced stress, increased motivation, and better workplace relationships, ultimately contributing to higher productivity and organizational performance (Freeman and Medoff, 1984). Conversely, organizations that suppress employee voice often witness increased job dissatisfaction, burnout, and workplace conflicts, which may affect employee retention and

* Corresponding author: Amah Cletus Okey.

overall well-being (Wilkinson et al., 2018). Despite the growing body of literature on employee voice and well-being, research on its impact within Nigeria's oil and gas sector remains limited. This is concerning, given the unique challenges employees face in the industry, such as job insecurity, exposure to hazardous conditions, and managerial practices that may not always support open communication. Moreover, existing studies on worker well-being in Nigeria have predominantly focused on issues such as job stress, work-life balance, and safety concerns (Akinwale and George, 2020), with little emphasis on the role of employee voice as a moderating factor.

In the oil and gas industry, where work environments are often high-risk and physically demanding, employee well-being is a critical issue. However, the extent to which employee voice influences worker well-being in this sector remains underexplored. Many organizations in Nigeria, including those in Rivers State, still operate within hierarchical structures that limit employee participation in decision-making processes. As a result, workers may feel disengaged, undervalued, and unsupported, leading to higher stress levels, reduced morale, and increased turnover rates. While studies have established that employee voice can improve workplace outcomes in developed economies (Bryson et al., 2013), there is a dearth of empirical evidence on its effects in Nigeria's oil and gas sector. Furthermore, the role of organizational policies, leadership styles, and industrial relations frameworks in shaping employee voice and its impact on well-being remains unclear. Given the sector's significance to Nigeria's economy and the ongoing labor disputes and safety concerns in the industry, understanding the relationship between employee voice and worker well-being is crucial for developing policies that promote a healthier and more productive workforce. This study seeks to fill this gap by examining the extent to which employee voice influences worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

1.1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Adapted from Akinwale, and George, (2020), Bakker, and Demerouti, (2007), Bryson, Freeman, Gomez, and Willman, (2013); Dundon, Wilkinson, Marchington, and Ackers, (2004); Freeman, and Medoff, (1984), Guest, (2017) and Wilkinson, Barry and Morrison, (2018).

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework for Employee Voice and Worker Well-being

The conceptual framework for this study illustrates the relationship between employee voice and worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. Employee voice serves as the independent variable, encompassing dimensions such as direct participation (e.g., suggestion systems, team meetings), indirect participation (e.g., labor unions, collective bargaining), and informal voice mechanisms (open-door policies, whistleblowing) (Dundon et al., 2004; Wilkinson et al., 2018). Worker well-being, the dependent variable, is conceptualized through physical well-being (occupational health and safety), psychological well-being (job satisfaction, stress levels), and social well-being (workplace relationships, engagement levels) (Guest, 2017; Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). Mediating

variables such as organizational policies, leadership style, and workplace culture may influence the strength of this relationship (Bryson et al., 2013). Moderating variables, including job security, employee autonomy, and industrial relations practices, may either enhance or weaken the impact of employee voice on well-being (Akinwale and George, 2020). The framework suggests that when employees feel empowered to express their concerns and contribute to decision-making, their well-being improves, leading to higher productivity, reduced turnover, and a more engaged workforce (Freeman and Medoff, 1984).

1.2. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine the relationship between employee voice and worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, the study is guided by the following objectives

- To examine the relationship between employee direct voice (e.g., suggestion systems, team meetings) and worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- To determine the relationship between employee indirect voice (e.g., labor unions, collective bargaining) and worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- To investigate the relationship between employee grievance procedures and worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

1.3. Research Questions

In line with the purpose of this study and the identified research problem, the following research questions are formulated

- How does employee direct voice (e.g., suggestion systems, team meetings) influence worker psychological social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- What is the relationship between employee indirect voice (e.g., labor unions, collective bargaining) and worker social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- To what extent do employee grievance procedures impact worker physical well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- How does employee direct voice (e.g., suggestion systems, team meetings) influence worker psychological well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- What is the relationship between employee indirect voice (e.g., labor unions, collective bargaining) and worker social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- To what extent do employee grievance procedures impact worker physical well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- How does employee direct voice (e.g., suggestion systems, team meetings) influence worker psychological well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- What is the relationship between employee indirect voice (e.g., labor unions, collective bargaining) and worker social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- To what extent do employee grievance procedures impact worker physical well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?

1.4. Research Hypotheses

In furtherance the stated objectives, the following tentative answers were provided for the foregoing research questions, as hypotheses, to be tested for empirical confirmation of the direction and strength of possible relationships.

- **H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between employee direct voice and psychological well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between employee direct voice and social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship between employee direct voice and physical well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₄:** There is no significant relationship between employee indirect voice and psychological well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₅:** There is no significant relationship between employee indirect voice and social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

- **H₀₆:** There is no significant relationship between employee indirect voice and physical well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₇:** There is no significant relationship between employee grievance procedure and psychological well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₈:** There is no significant relationship between employee grievance procedure and social well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- **H₀₉:** There is no significant relationship between employee grievance procedure and physical well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

2. Literature review

2.1. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored on the Organizational Justice Theory and Value Fulfillment Theory, both of which provide insights into the relationship between employee voice and worker well-being in selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The Organizational Justice Theory explains how fairness in decision-making processes, resource distribution, and interpersonal interactions within an organization influences employee perceptions and behaviors. According to Greenberg (1990) and Tyler (1987), employees assess fairness based on three dimensions: distributive justice, which concerns the perceived fairness of outcomes; procedural justice, which relates to the fairness of decision-making processes; and interactional justice, which emphasizes respectful and dignified treatment of employees. When employees perceive fairness in these aspects, they are more likely to feel valued, satisfied, and engaged in their work, leading to enhanced well-being. Conversely, an absence of justice in the workplace can lead to stress, dissatisfaction, and disengagement, thereby negatively impacting worker well-being (Bies and Moag, 1986; Masterson et al., 2000).

The Value Fulfillment Theory, as proposed by Tiberius (2018), offers a complementary perspective by emphasizing that individuals' well-being is closely linked to the fulfillment of their values, which guide their goals and aspirations. In the workplace, employees derive well-being when their work environment aligns with their personal values, including psychological, social, and professional aspirations (Elizur and Sagie, 1999; Ueda and Ohzono, 2012). This theory suggests that an individual's sense of well-being is heightened when they engage in work that aligns with their intrinsic motivations and aspirations, thereby reinforcing the importance of employee voice as a mechanism for achieving value fulfillment in the workplace. Employees who are given the opportunity to express their concerns, ideas, and opinions feel a greater sense of control over their work environment, which enhances their satisfaction and overall well-being (Raibley, 2010).

2.2. Conceptual Review

2.2.1. Employee Voice

Employee voice refers to the mechanisms through which employees express their opinions, concerns, and suggestions about workplace conditions and organizational decisions (Dundon et al., 2004). It can be categorized into formal voice channels, such as grievance procedures, union representation, and participation in decision-making bodies, and informal voice channels, such as direct feedback to supervisors and open-door policies (Wilkinson et al., 2018). Research suggests that employee voice enhances job satisfaction, reduces workplace stress, and fosters trust between employees and management, ultimately improving organizational performance (Bryson et al., 2013). However, in many organizations, particularly in hierarchical and authoritarian work environments, employee voice is often stifled, leading to increased frustration and disengagement (Morrison, 2011).

2.2.2. Worker Well-Being

Worker well-being is a multidimensional concept that includes physical, psychological, and social aspects (Guest, 2017). Physical well-being focuses on occupational health and safety, ensuring that employees are protected from workplace hazards. Psychological well-being relates to job satisfaction, stress management, and emotional stability at work (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007). Social well-being involves positive workplace relationships, inclusion, and a sense of belonging (Akinwale and George, 2020). Studies have shown that organizations that prioritize worker well-being experience lower absenteeism, higher engagement levels, and improved overall productivity (Van De Voorde et al., 2012).

2.3. Empirical Review

2.3.1. *Relationship between Employee Voice and Worker Well-Being*

The link between employee voice and worker well-being has been widely studied, with evidence suggesting that workplaces that encourage open communication tend to have more satisfied, engaged, and healthier employees (Freeman and Medoff, 1984). Employee participation in decision-making enhances their sense of control over their work environment, leading to reduced stress and improved motivation (Wilkinson et al., 2018). Conversely, workplaces that suppress employee voice often experience higher turnover rates, lower job satisfaction, and increased workplace conflicts (Bryson et al., 2013). Research suggests that organizations that provide employees with opportunities to express concerns, participate in decision-making, and engage in dialogue experience higher levels of worker satisfaction and productivity (Marchington, 2001). Studies have shown that employee voice mechanisms, particularly through unions, enhance worker well-being by promoting fair wages, reducing workplace inequalities, and improving working conditions (Freeman, 1980; Booth, 1995; Clark and Oswald, 1996; Card et al., 2003; Blanchflower and Bryson, 2004). Additionally, empirical evidence supports the notion that employee participation in decision-making improves psychological well-being and reduces stress, contributing to long-term employee retention and commitment (Budd and Na, 2000; Metcalf et al., 2001; Hirsch, 2004).

Beyond wages, unions and collective voice mechanisms have been associated with improved access to training, job security, and enhanced occupational health and safety standards (Booth, 1991; Acemoglu et al., 2001; Waddoups, 2012). These factors positively affect workers' well-being by reducing job-related uncertainties and ensuring that employees feel valued and supported. Furthermore, representative voice structures such as collective bargaining and consultative bodies have been linked to improvements in social and psychological well-being, as they foster an inclusive work environment and facilitate workplace equity (Buchmueller et al., 2002; Donado and Walde, 2012; Budd and Mumford, 2004).

2.3.2. *Relationship between Employee Direct Voice and Worker Well-Being*

Employee direct voice refers to employees' ability to engage in dialogue with management, participate in decision-making, and express workplace concerns without intermediaries. Empirical studies indicate that direct voice mechanisms, such as team meetings, quality circles, and open-door policies, significantly contribute to psychological well-being by fostering autonomy, self-respect, and job satisfaction (Marginson et al., 2010; Grant et al., 2007). European Union labor policies highlight the importance of employee direct voice in improving motivation and well-being (Budd and Zagelmeyer, 2010).

Direct employee voice has been associated with improved job performance, self-efficacy, and personal growth (Boxall and Macky, 2014; Gallie and Zhou, 2013). Studies further emphasize that workplaces with direct communication channels experience higher levels of trust, engagement, and reduced turnover rates (Parker, 2003; Klein et al., 2000; Cotton et al., 1988). Research also suggests that direct employee involvement enhances work-life balance, reducing burnout and stress-related issues in the workplace.

2.3.3. *Relationship between Employee Indirect Voice and Worker Well-Being*

Indirect employee voice, often facilitated through union representation, consultative committees, and collective bargaining, has been extensively studied for its impact on worker well-being. Empirical findings suggest that organizations with structured indirect voice mechanisms experience higher employee satisfaction and social well-being (Tarela, 2017). Indirect voice fosters a sense of belonging, trust, and mutual support among workers, contributing to an inclusive and collaborative work environment (Jenn et al., 2016).

Union representation has been linked to greater job security, equitable wages, and access to benefits such as health insurance and pension plans, all of which improve overall well-being (Kim et al., 2010; Markey et al., 2010). Moreover, research highlights that collective bargaining enhances social well-being by promoting workplace democracy, fair treatment, and representation in key decision-making processes (Freeman and Medoff, 1984). Evidence suggests that employees in unionized jobs experience less workplace discrimination and greater work-life balance compared to their non-unionized counterparts (Budd and Mumford, 2004). A well-structured grievance procedure is essential in maintaining employee well-being and fostering workplace harmony. Studies indicate that effective grievance resolution systems contribute to employee psychological and physical well-being by addressing workplace concerns and ensuring fair treatment (Cohen-Powless et al., 2003; Diener et al., 1995). Organizations with transparent grievance procedures tend to have more engaged employees who feel valued and respected (Lewin, 2014).

Research indicates that unresolved grievances can lead to job dissatisfaction, increased stress, and higher turnover rates, negatively impacting both employees and the organization (Frey and Stutzer, 2010). Conversely, workplaces with efficient grievance mechanisms see improvements in employee morale, trust, and workplace cohesion. Additionally, a fair and just grievance system contributes to social well-being by reinforcing workplace equity and fostering a culture of inclusivity and respect. In the Nigerian oil and gas sector, where job insecurity, safety risks, and managerial autocracy are prevalent, the role of employee voice in shaping worker well-being is crucial (Akinwale and George, 2020). Given the industry's labor-intensive nature and frequent industrial disputes, understanding how employee voice can contribute to a healthier work environment is essential for both policy formulation and organizational sustainability.

3. Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design, which is suitable for capturing data at a single point in time. Cross-sectional surveys help in assessing the frequency or level of attributes within a defined population. The choice of this design is justified as it provides a snapshot of the situation within the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria, enabling an analysis of organizational dynamics at a given time (Saunders et al., 2009). The population of the study consists of employees from ten selected oil and gas producing companies in Rivers State. These firms were chosen based on their classification as oil and gas producers with annual production exceeding 3,000,000 barrels and the presence of their zonal offices in Rivers State. The total population of employees across the ten companies is 630. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's (1970) formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

where

- n = sample size
- N = total population (630)
- e = level of significance (0.05)

$$n = \frac{630}{1 + 630(0.0025)^2} = \frac{630}{2.575} = 245$$

Thus, the sample size for this study is 245 respondents. The proportionate sampling technique was applied using Bowley's proportional allocation formula to distribute the sample among the ten firms:

$$nh = \frac{nNh}{Nn}$$

where

- nh = sample size for each company
- Nh = population of each company
- N = total population (630)
- n = total sample size (245)

The calculated sample distribution across the selected firms is presented in the table below.

Table 1 Proportionate Sample Distribution

Names of Companies	Population	Sample Size Distribution
Masters Energy Limited	47	18
Eroton Exploration	59	23
Newcross Exploration	61	24
Total EandP Nigeria Limited	53	21
Agip Energy and Natural Limited	74	29
Chevron Texaco Nigeria Limited	51	20
Exxon Mobil Nigeria Limited	45	18
Niger Delta Exploration and Production	68	25
Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd	107	42
Belema Oil Producing Limited	65	25
Total	630	245

Source: Research Survey, 2024

Primary data collection was adopted through the use of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of two sections: Section One captures the demographic characteristics of respondents, while Section Two consists of study variables, with Segment A, B, and C addressing dimensions of the independent variable (employee voice) and the measures of the criterion variable (workers’ well-being). The questionnaire employs a five-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) to ensure consistency in responses and unbiased participation.

The study employed content and face validity to ensure the adequacy and relevance of the research instrument. Experts, including the course lecturer and other scholars in the field, reviewed the questionnaire to ensure clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. Reliability was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha, which measures internal consistency. According to Nunally’s (1971) benchmark, a coefficient (α) of 0.70 or above is considered acceptable (Baridam, 2001). The reliability coefficients for the study variables ranged from 0.779 to 0.876, indicating adequate reliability.

Table 2 Cronbach’s Alpha of Study Variables

No. of Items	Variables	Alpha (α)
4	Direct Voice	0.779
4	Indirect Voice	0.861
4	Employee Grievance Procedures	0.828
4	Psychological Well-being	0.822
4	Psychological Well-being	0.876
4	Physical Well-being	0.828

Source: Research Data, 2024

The analysis was conducted in three stages. The primary stage involved descriptive analysis using frequency tables and charts to present demographic data. At the secondary stage, univariate analysis was employed to describe individual study variables, using measures of central tendency (mean scores) and dispersion (standard deviation) to ensure normality in distribution. At the tertiary stage, bivariate analysis was conducted to determine the strength and direction of relationships between the predictor and criterion variables using Spearman’s Rank Order Correlation Coefficient. Hypothesis testing was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. These analytical techniques provided a comprehensive approach to examining the relationship between employee voice and workers’ well-being in the selected oil and gas companies.

4. Results and Interpretations

Table 3 Distributions and Retrieved Copies of Questionnaire

Detailed Response Rate	Distributed Copies	Retrieved Copies	Not Retrieved Copies	Discarded Copies	Used Copies
Total	245(100%)	234(95.5%)	11(4.5%)	3(1.3%)	231(94.2%)

Source: Research Survey, 2024

The table presents the distribution and retrieval rate of the questionnaires used in the study. Out of 245 questionnaires distributed (100%), 234 were successfully retrieved, representing a high response rate of 95.5%. However, 11 questionnaires (4.5%) were not returned. Additionally, 3 retrieved copies (1.3%) were discarded due to errors or incomplete responses, leaving 231 valid copies (94.2%) for analysis. The high response and usability rates indicate strong participant engagement and data reliability.

4.1. Demographic Analysis

Demographics are quantifiable characteristics of a given population. The demographics of this study covered areas such as age, gender, education and year of experience.

Table 4 Gender of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	192	83.1	83.1	83.1
	Female	39	16.9	16.9	100.0
	Total	231	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

Table 4 shows the gender distribution of respondents. Out of 231 valid responses, 192 (83.1%) were male, while 39 (16.9%) were female. This indicates that the majority of the respondents in the study were male, reflecting a gender imbalance in the sampled population. The cumulative percentage confirms that all responses were accounted for, with 100% representation. See the bar chart for the gender of the respondents.

Figure 2 Gender of respondents

Table 5 Age of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 25 Years	28	12.1	12.1	12.1
	26-35 Years	72	31.2	31.2	43.3
	36-45 Years	89	38.5	38.5	81.8
	46 Years and Above	42	18.2	18.2	100.0
	Total	231	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The table presents the age distribution of respondents. Out of 231 valid responses, 28 (12.1%) were less than 25 years old, 72 (31.2%) were between 26 and 35 years, 89 (38.5%) fell within the 36 to 45 years range, and 42 (18.2%) were 46 years and above. The largest age group was 36–45 years, representing 38.5% of the respondents, indicating that the majority of the workforce in the sampled oil and gas companies falls within this middle-age bracket. The cumulative percentage confirms that all responses were fully accounted for. See figure 3 the bar chart for the frequencies and percentages of the age of the respondents.

Figure 3 Age of respondents

Table 6 Educational Qualification of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma Certificate	31	13.4	13.4	13.4
	Graduate Degree	83	35.9	35.9	49.4
	Post-Graduate Degree	51	22.1	22.1	71.4
	Others Cert	66	28.6	28.6	100.0
	Total	231	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The table shows the educational qualifications of respondents. Out of 231 valid responses, 31 (13.4%) hold a diploma certificate, 83 (35.9%) have a graduate degree, 51 (22.1%) possess a postgraduate degree, while 66 (28.6%) falls under

other certification categories. The majority of respondents (35.9%) are graduate degree holders, indicating a relatively high level of education among employees in the sampled oil and gas companies.

Figure 4 Educational level of respondents

Table 7 Tenure with the Organization

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 5 years	25	10.8	10.8	10.8
	6 - 10 years	69	29.9	29.9	40.7
	11 - 15 years	87	37.7	37.7	78.4
	16 Years and Above	50	21.6	21.6	100.0
	Total	231	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The table presents the tenure of respondents within their organizations. Out of 231 valid responses, 25 (10.8%) have worked for less than five years, 69 (29.9%) have been with their organization for 6 to 10 years, 87 (37.7%) have served for 11 to 15 years, while 50 (21.6%) have been employed for 16 years or more. The majority (37.7%) have been with their organization for 11 to 15 years, suggesting a relatively experienced workforce in the sampled oil and gas companies.

Figure 5 Years of working experience

Table 8 Assessment of Descriptive Statistic

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Employee Voice	Mean	3.6385	.04725	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.5454	
		Upper Bound	3.7316	
	5% Trimmed Mean	3.7048		
	Median	3.8333		
	Variance	0.516		
	Std. Deviation	.71812		
	Minimum	1.83		
	Maximum	4.25		
	Range	2.42		
	Interquartile Range	0.25		
	Skewness	-1.871	0.160	
Kurtosis	2.024	0.319		
Worker Well-Being	Mean	3.6833	0.05372	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.5774	
		Upper Bound	3.7891	
	5% Trimmed Mean	3.7453		
	Median	3.9167		
	Variance0	0.667		

	Std. Deviation	.81644	
	Minimum	1.92	
	Maximum	4.33	
	Range	2.42	
	Interquartile Range	0.33	
	Skewness	-1.504	0.160
	Kurtosis	0.495	0.319

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The table presents the descriptive statistics for Employee Voice and Worker Well-Being. The mean score for Employee Voice is 3.64, with a standard deviation of 0.72, indicating moderate agreement among respondents. The skewness of -1.871 suggests a negatively skewed distribution, while the kurtosis of 2.024 indicates a leptokurtic distribution. Worker Well-Being has a mean score of 3.68 with a standard deviation of 0.82, also showing moderate agreement. The skewness of -1.504 suggests a leftward skew, while the kurtosis of 0.495 indicates a relatively normal distribution. Both variables exhibit a range of 2.42, showing variability in responses.

Table 9 Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Employee Voice	0.376	231	0.000	0.641	231	0.000
Worker Well-Being	0.387	231	0.000	0.647	231	0.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The normality test results indicate that both Employee Voice and Worker Well-Being do not follow a normal distribution. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests yield significance values (Sig.) of 0.000 for both variables, which are below the 0.05 threshold. This suggests a statistically significant deviation from normality. Therefore, non-parametric statistical methods may be more appropriate for further analysis.

Table 10 Correlations for Direct Voice and The Measures of Worker Well-Being

			Direct Voice	Psychological Well-being	Social Well-being	Physical Well-being
Spearman's rho	Direct Voice	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.729**	0.718**	0.750**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Psychological Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	0.729**	1.000	0.742**	0.781**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Social Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	0.718**	0.742**	1.000	0.794**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231

	Physical Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	0.750**	0.781**	0.794**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The correlation results indicate a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between Employee Direct Voice and all measures of Worker Well-Being (Psychological, Social, and Physical Well-Being). The Spearman's correlation coefficients range from 0.718 to 0.750, all significant at the 0.01 level. This suggests that as Employee Direct Voice increases, worker well-being in all three dimensions also improves. Additionally, the interrelationships among the well-being measures are also strong, with the highest correlation observed between Physical and Social Well-Being (0.794). These findings imply that fostering employee voice can significantly enhance overall worker well-being.

Table 11 Correlations for Indirect Voice and The Measures of Worker Well-Being

			Indirect Voice	Psychological Well-being	Social Well-being	Physical Well-being
Spearman's rho	Indirect Voice	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.647**	0.622**	0.617**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Psychological Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	.647**	1.000	.642**	.681**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Social Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	.622**	.642**	1.000	.694**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Physical Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	0.617**	0.681**	0.694**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	.
		N	231	231	231	231

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The correlation results indicate a significant positive relationship between Indirect Voice and all measures of Worker Well-Being (Psychological, Social, and Physical Well-Being), with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.617 to 0.647, all significant at the 0.01 level. This suggests that an increase in Indirect Voice is associated with improvements in worker well-being, though the strength of these correlations is slightly weaker compared to Direct Voice. Among the well-being measures, the strongest relationship is observed between Psychological and Physical Well-Being (0.681) and between Social and Physical Well-Being (0.694), indicating a close link between different dimensions of worker well-being. These findings highlight that while Indirect Voice contributes to worker well-being, its impact may be relatively lower than that of Direct Voice.

Table 12 Correlations for Leadership Style and The Measures of Worker Well-Being

			Leadership Style	Psychological Well-being	Social Well-being	Physical Well-being
Spearman's rho	Leadership Style	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.775**	.643**	.606**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Psychological Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	.775**	1.000	.542**	.681**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Social Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	0.643**	0.542**	1.000	0.694**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231
	Physical Well-being	Correlation Coefficient	0.606**	0.681**	0.694**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		N	231	231	231	231

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 Source: SPSS Output, 2024

The correlation analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between Leadership Style and all measures of Worker Well-Being (Psychological, Social, and Physical Well-Being), with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.606 to 0.775, all significant at the 0.01 level. The strongest relationship is between Leadership Style and Psychological Well-Being (0.775), suggesting that effective leadership strongly influences employees' mental and emotional stability. Social and Physical Well-Being also show positive correlations with Leadership Style, but with lower strength (0.643 and 0.606, respectively), indicating that leadership plays a crucial role in fostering workplace relationships and employees' physical health. Additionally, there are strong interrelationships among the well-being measures, with Social and Physical Well-Being showing a correlation of 0.694, and Psychological and Physical Well-Being at 0.681. These results suggest that a supportive and effective leadership style significantly enhances employees' overall well-being, particularly their psychological and social health.

5. Discussion of Findings

The results highlight the significant role of employee voice (direct and indirect) and leadership style in shaping worker well-being, covering psychological, social, and physical dimensions.

5.1. Employee Direct and Indirect Voice and Worker Well-Being

The findings reveal a strong positive relationship between Direct Voice and worker well-being, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.718 to 0.750. This suggests that when employees have direct channels to express their opinions and concerns, their psychological, social, and physical well-being improves significantly. This aligns with prior studies, such as Dundon et al. (2004) and Wilkinson et al. (2018), which emphasize that direct participation mechanisms, such as open-door policies, team meetings, and employee feedback systems, enhance job satisfaction and overall well-being. The high correlation between direct voice and physical well-being (0.750) suggests that open communication channels may reduce stress and workplace hazards, contributing to better health outcomes.

On the other hand, Indirect Voice, which involves representation through trade unions or employee representatives, also shows a significant but slightly weaker correlation with worker well-being (0.617 to 0.647). This finding aligns with research by Bryson (2004) and Gollan (2006), who argue that while indirect voice mechanisms improve job security

and advocacy, their impact on immediate well-being is less pronounced compared to direct engagement. The slightly lower correlation compared to direct voice suggests that employees may perceive indirect representation as less immediate or effective in addressing their concerns.

5.2. Leadership Style and Worker Well-Being

Leadership style exhibits a strong positive correlation with worker well-being, with the highest impact observed on psychological well-being (0.775). This suggests that effective leadership fosters a positive work environment, reducing stress and increasing job satisfaction. These findings support Bass and Avolio's (1994) Transformational Leadership Theory, which posits that leaders who inspire, motivate, and support employees contribute to better mental and emotional well-being. The moderate correlations between leadership style and social well-being (0.643) and physical well-being (0.606) indicate that good leadership fosters workplace relationships and enhances safety and health conditions. This finding aligns with Podsakoff et al. (1996), who suggest that supportive leadership reduces workplace conflicts and enhances teamwork, indirectly improving social and physical well-being. The positive correlation with physical well-being suggests that a leadership approach emphasizing employee welfare, health initiatives, and work-life balance contributes to better physical health outcomes.

6. Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the critical role of employee voice (both direct and indirect) and leadership style in enhancing worker well-being across psychological, social, and physical dimensions. Direct Voice exhibited the strongest relationship with worker well-being, suggesting that open communication channels significantly improve job satisfaction, reduce workplace stress, and enhance overall health outcomes. While Indirect Voice also contributed positively to well-being, its impact was slightly weaker, indicating that employees may perceive direct engagement as more effective in addressing their concerns. Similarly, leadership style showed a strong influence on worker well-being, particularly psychological well-being, reinforcing the importance of transformational leadership in fostering a supportive and motivating work environment. Based on these findings, organizations should prioritize policies that encourage direct employee participation, such as open-door policies, feedback mechanisms, and collaborative decision-making structures. While indirect representation through unions remains important, efforts should be made to strengthen its effectiveness in addressing employee concerns. Furthermore, leadership development programs should focus on fostering transformational leadership qualities that enhance psychological and social well-being. Organizations should also integrate well-being initiatives, such as workplace health programs and work-life balance policies, to further improve employees' physical and mental health. Implementing these recommendations will create a more engaged, satisfied, and productive workforce.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Acemoglu, D., Aghion, P., and Violante, G. L. (2001). Deunionization, technical change, and inequality. *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 55(1), 229-264.
- [2] Akinwale, O. E., and George, O. J. (2020). Work environment and well-being: Mediating role of work engagement among frontline employees. *Employee Relations*, 42(4), 903-919.
- [3] Bailey, C., and Madden, A. (2017). Time reclaimed: Temporality and well-being in the workplace. *Work, Employment and Society*, 31(4), 551-567.
- [4] Bakker, A. B., and Demerouti, E. (2007). The Job Demands-Resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309-328.
- [5] Bass, B. M., and Avolio, B. J. (1994). *Improving organizational effectiveness through transformational leadership*. SAGE Publications.

- [6] Bies, R. J., and Moag, J. S. (1986). Interactional justice: Communication criteria of fairness. *Research on Negotiation in Organizations*, 1, 43-55.
- [7] Blanchflower, D. G., and Bryson, A. (2004). What effect do unions have on wages now and would Freeman and Medoff be surprised? *Journal of Labor Research*, 25(3), 383-414.
- [8] Booth, A. L. (1991). Job-related formal training: Who receives it and what is it worth? *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 53(3), 281-294.
- [9] Booth, A. L. (1995). *The economics of the trade union*. Cambridge University Press.
- [10] Booth, A. L., Francesconi, M., and Zoega, G. (2003). Unions, work-related training, and wages: Evidence for British men. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 57(1), 68-91.
- [11] Bryson, A. (2004). Managerial responsiveness to union and nonunion worker voice in Britain. *Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society*, 43(1), 213-241.
- [12] Bryson, A., and Freeman, R. B. (2013). *Employee voice and the economic crisis*. National Bureau of Economic Research.
- [13] Bryson, A., Freeman, R. B., Gomez, R., and Willman, P. (2013). The role of employee voice in organizational success. In A. Wilkinson, J. Donaghey, T. Dundon, and R. B. Freeman (Eds.), *Handbook of Research on Employee Voice* (pp. 29-50). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- [14] Buchmueller, T. C., DiNardo, J., and Valletta, R. G. (2002). Union effects on health insurance provision and coverage in the United States. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 55(4), 610-627.
- [15] Budd, J. W., and Mumford, K. A. (2004). Trade unions and family-friendly policies in Britain. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 57(2), 204-222.
- [16] Budd, J. W., and Na, I. (2000). The union membership wage premium puzzle. *Journal of Labor Research*, 21(3), 423-436.
- [17] Budd, J. W., and Zagelmeyer, S. (2010). Public policy and employee participation. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21(13), 2513-2530.
- [18] Card, D. (1996). The effect of unions on the structure of wages: A longitudinal analysis. *Econometrica*, 64(4), 957-979.
- [19] Card, D., Lemieux, T., and Riddell, W. C. (2003). Unionization and wage inequality: A comparative study of the U.S., the U.K., and Canada. National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper No. 9473.
- [20] Clark, A. E., and Oswald, A. J. (1996). Satisfaction and comparison income. *Journal of Public Economics*, 61(3), 359-381.
- [21] Cohen-Powless, J., Rogelberg, S. G., and Luong, A. (2003). Workplace grievance procedures and well-being. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 8(4), 271-286.
- [22] Cotton, J. L., Vollrath, D. A., Froggatt, K. L., Lengnick-Hall, M. L., and Jennings, K. R. (1988). Employee participation: Diverse forms and different outcomes. *Academy of Management Review*, 13(1), 8-22.
- [23] Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., and Smith, H. L. (1995). Subjective well-being: Three decades of progress. *Psychological Bulletin*, 125(2), 276-302.
- [24] Donado, A., and Wälde, K. (2012). How trade unions increase welfare. *The Economic Journal*, 122(563), 990-1009.
- [25] Dundon, T., Wilkinson, A., Marchington, M., and Ackers, P. (2004). The meanings and purpose of employee voice. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(6), 1149-1170.
- [26] Dundon, T., Wilkinson, A., Marchington, M., and Ackers, P. (2004). The meanings and purpose of employee voice. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(6), 1149-1170.
- [27] Dundon, T., Wilkinson, A., Marchington, M., and Ackers, P. (2004). The meanings and purpose of employee voice. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(6), 1149-1170.
- [28] Elizur, D., and Sagie, A. (1999). Facets of work values: A structural analysis of work outcomes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 84(4), 453-468.
- [29] Freeman, R. B. (1980). Unionism and the dispersion of wages. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 34(1), 3-23.

- [30] Freeman, R. B., and Medoff, J. L. (1984). *What do unions do?* Basic Books.
- [31] Freeman, R. B., and Medoff, J. L. (1984). *What do unions do?* Basic Books.
- [32] Frey, B. S., and Stutzer, A. (2010). *Happiness and economics: How the economy and institutions affect human well-being.* Princeton University Press.
- [33] Gallie, D., and Zhou, Y. (2013). Work organization and employee involvement in Europe. *European Sociological Review*, 29(5), 802-818.
- [34] Gollan, P. J. (2006). *Employee representation in non-union firms.* SAGE Publications.
- [35] Gosling, A., and Machin, S. (1995). Trade unions and the dispersion of earnings in British establishments, 1980–1990. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 57(2), 167-184.
- [36] Grant, A. M., Christianson, M. K., and Price, R. H. (2007). Happiness, health, or relationships? Managerial practices and employee well-being tradeoffs. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 21(3), 51-63.
- [37] Greenberg, J. (1990). Organizational justice: Yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *Journal of Management*, 16(2), 399-432.
- [38] Guest, D. E. (2017). Human resource management and employee well-being: Towards a new analytic framework. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(1), 22-38.
- [39] Hirsch, B. T. (2004). Reconsidering union wage effects: Surveying new evidence on an old topic. *Journal of Labor Research*, 25(2), 233-266.
- [40] Jenn, M., Claudia, H., Howard, A., and Amy, L. (2016). Unions, social capital, and well-being. *Journal of Labor Relations*, 52(3), 315-335.
- [41] Kim, D., Markey, R., and Jang, S. (2010). Employee voice and well-being: Evidence from workplace representation in South Korea. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 41(5), 485-504.
- [42] Kwon, B., and Farndale, E. (2020). Employee voice viewed differently: The impact of perspective-taking on engagement and well-being. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 30(1), 157-173.
- [43] Lewin, D. (2014). Workplace dispute resolution. *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 56(1), 24-50.
- [44] Malcomson, J. M. (1983). Trade unions and economic efficiency. *Economic Journal*, 93(369), 50-65.
- [45] Marchington, M. (2001). Employee involvement: Patterns and explanations. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 11(3), 50-67.
- [46] Masterson, S. S., Lewis, K., Goldman, B. M., and Taylor, M. S. (2000). Integrating justice and social exchange: The differing effects of fair procedures and treatment on work relationships. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43(4), 738-748.
- [47] Metcalf, D., Hansen, K., and Charlwood, A. (2001). Unions and the sword of justice. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 32(2), 94-120.
- [48] Morrison, E. W. (2011). Employee voice behavior: Integration and directions for future research. *Academy of Management Annals*, 5(1), 373-412.
- [49] Peccei, R., Van De Voorde, K., and Van Veldhoven, M. (2013). HRM, well-being, and performance: A theoretical and empirical review. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 23(4), 227-233.
- [50] Phanindra, V., and Peled, A. (1999). Workplace diversity and union discrimination policies. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*, 52(4), 608-626.
- [51] Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Moorman, R. H., and Fetter, R. (1996). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, trust, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259–298.
- [52] Raibley, J. R. (2010). Well-being and the priority of values. *Social Theory and Practice*, 36(2), 209-248.
- [53] Tiberius, V. (2018). *Well-being as value fulfillment: How we can help each other to live well.* Oxford University Press.
- [54] Tyler, T. R. (1987). Conditions leading to value-expressive effects in judgments of procedural justice: A test of four models. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 52(2), 333-344.

- [55] Ueda, Y., and Ohzono, Y. (2012). The relationship between work values and motivation to work among Japanese employees. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(6), 60-70.
- [56] Wilkinson, A., Barry, M., and Morrison, E. W. (2018). Toward an integration of research on employee voice. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 28(3), 414-433.
- [57] Wilkinson, A., Donaghey, J., Dundon, T., and Freeman, R. (2014). *Handbook of Research on Employee Voice*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- [58] Wilkinson, A., Dundon, T., Donaghey, J., and Freeman, R. B. (Eds.). (2018). *Handbook of research on employee voice*. Edward Elgar Publishing.